

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING VOCABULARY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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In analyzing the different methods of word formation, it is expedient to consider the classification of neologisms proposed by Louis Gilbert. At this point, it is important to highlight key word formation models. We conduct our research based on the above classification. Louis Gilbert proposed to distinguish the following groups of neologisms according to the method of construction:

Phonological neologisms formed from individual sounds or their specific combination. In this type of neologisms, some artificial signs are noticeable. This type of sound combination is often combined with morphemes derived from Greek or Latin. Examples of this are neologisms denoting substance names: antiozonant, humectant, propellant, antipyretic. Terms used in physics, chemistry, optics, and other sciences are also examples: interploidy, triploid, aquaregia, emollient, zeolite. Such neologisms are absolute phonological neologisms. This group can also include neologisms (pronouns neologisms): zizz, tobuzz, snap. Undoubtedly, the basis of neologisms made of pronouns is the implication of sounds and imitative sounds. Finally, we can also conditionally add new pronouns to this group, such as bazinga, yippee, whammo, yowza.

Morphological neologisms based on existing methods and morphemes in the language system. We will discuss them in more detail below. A) Affixal neologisms. The affixes used in the creation of new words and in their distribution are many and varied today. Naturally, the novelty feature is high in units created using new affixes and semi-affixes. The number of such affixes is not very large. Commonly used affixes are: -on, -ase, -gate, -sd, -nik, -natcher, -ity, -ment, -manship suffixes andeco-, mini-, maxi-, mega-, cine-, -oholic, a-, flexi-like prefixes. An important feature of affixes used in modern English is that they are terminological and specific to a particular scientific and technical field. For example, accompaniment, acetylcholine, serendipity. There are three main types of affixes : Prefixes, infixes, and suffixes. A prefix occurs at the beginning of a word (sub- mit, pre-determine). A suffix at the end (wonder-ful, act-ion) and an infix occurs in the middle. There are no infixes in English, but they are found in American Indian languages, Greek and elsewhere Most word-formation models

are the result of the separation of word-formation elements from neologisms, i.e., affixes expand or change their meaning, e.g. This neologism has expanded its meaning. For example the affix *aholic* separated from the workaholic neologism (*biron bir narsaga mukkasidan berilib ketish*, *kirishib ketish*): *chocoholic*, *danceaholic*, *shopaholic*. In the same way, word-forming elements (affixes) such as *super-*, *counter-*, *anti-*, *-ism* have also changed and expanded their meaning.

B) Word addition. Neologisms formed by word addition are divided into types such as nouns, adjectives and verbs according to their syntactic nature: Compound nouns are plural and include the following word-formation models: -Noun +Noun *earworm* (*miyada doim aylanib turadigan qo'shiq*) *mouse potato* (*ko'p vaqtini computer oldida o'tkazadigan kishi*); - Adjective + Noun: *long tail* (*marketing va tarqatish uchun qo'shimcha vaqt va xarajatlarni kamaytirish orqali katta foyda keltirishi mumkin bo'lgan yangi tovarlarning katta assortimentini sotish va hk.*);- Verb + Noun: *turnberry* (*eski asarlarni yangi niqob ostida sotish*); - Noun + Verb: In Modern English the most productive type of back-formation is derivation of verbs from compounds that have such elements as: *-er*, *-ing* at the end. Examples: *thought-read* v < *thought-reader* n < *thought-reading* n; *air-condition* v < *air-conditioner* n < *air-conditioning* n; *turbo-supercharge* v < *turbo-supercharger* n. Other examples of back- formations from compounds are: *beachcomb*, *house-break*, *house-clean*, *house-keep*, *red-bait*, *tape-record* [2:151].

Reduplication. In this type of word-formation new words are formed by doubling the stem of a word. A new word can be formed in two ways: 1) without any phonetic changes (*bye-bye* for *good-bye*), 2) with a modification of the root-vowel or consonant that is also called gradational reduplication (*ping-pong*, *chit-chat*). A vast number of new words, which are made by reduplication - are used in informal style: colloquial words and slang. Other examples: *walkie-talkie* ("a portable radio"), *riff-raff* ("the worthless or disreputable element of society"; "the dregs of society"), *chi-chi* (sl. for *chic* as in a *chichi* girl). In modern English, the following methods are used in the process of word formation: abbreviation, conversion, meaning differentiation, affixation, dizaffixation, word addition, compression. These methods of word formation can be used independently and together. In our study the classifications of neologisms made by Zabotkina V.I. and Louis Gilberts were considered. Based on the opinions of the linguists named above, we have divided neologisms into two major groups: phonological neologisms formed from independent sounds or their specific combination; morphological neologisms based on the morphemes of this system and samples of existing in the language system.

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